

In: J. Louçã e M. J. Ramos, *Proceedings of the International Meeting AI-Pocalypse: How AI is turning academia upside down – May 28th, 2025*. Available at <https://zenodo.org/communities/ai-pocalypse-1>

The Omniscient and Incompetent: Personal Reflections on Academia in the Age of AI

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Keywords: AI, academia, social sciences, Africa, optimization, plagiarism

Abstract

This is a personal essay written by a bewildered academic—anthropologist/Africanist based at Iscte in Lisbon—who tries to make sense of the AI revolution and its significance for his own work and that of his colleagues in Europe and in Africa. From his perspective as a non-specialist, the author reflects back on his early encounters with AI and his experiences with LLMs over the past year. While he sees AI as an opportunity for academics to focus more on real-world meaningful action such as public outreach, communicating recommendations, building transcultural bridges, and investing in extended in-person fieldwork, the author acknowledges that the rapid technological advancement makes the line between the “digital” and the “real” increasingly fuzzy. As an example, he discusses the case of an AI-generated final report for a workshop that haven’t yet took place, whose hallucinations challenge the common ethnographic advice of setting preconceptions and expectations aside before going to the field, raising questions about a strange feedback loop between machine imagination and actual futures. Above all, the author challenges himself to go beyond a narrow idea of AI as a tool for cutting academic corners and instead suggests that how AI will be used in academia depends on man-made incentive structures: If we come to see academia exclusively in terms of box-ticking for degree or promotion and if we put unrealistic pressures on both students and staff, or otherwise force

ourselves into neoliberal Darwinism of “survival of the optimised”, then desperation will surely feed temptations for AI to be promoted from a supportive role to a full-blown ghost writer.

Last summer (mid-2024), during a visit to a partner university in western Kenya, I was asked to give a workshop on grant writing to the university’s staff. I spoke for a while about funding opportunities and some principles that have worked for me in the past, and my hosts listened politely. We broke for lunch, and then came back for the second part, which, according to the program, would turn to discuss attendees’ own project application goals. We started off with some questions, at which point one participant, an older professor who was introduced to me as the head of research, looked at me and said something along the lines of, “well, how about you tell us how we get AI to write the projects for us?”

A year ago, the AI revolution still hasn’t reached me, and I was taken aback by the question and its unabashed directness. I have written my main research projects in the pre-AI era, and while my knowledge on the matter was—and still is—limited, my non-expert’s reaction was that asking AI to write a complete, competitive project proposal for us is more or less tantamount to cheating. To be honest, I also felt a bit annoyed, sensing that, with his question, the professor chipped away at the mystique of my precious skillset. Here I am, scouting the funding landscape and giving my two cents on the fine art of scientific innovation, and by asking for a shortcut, the professor was undermining it all. It felt terribly irreverent. But then again, maybe it was me who was being out of touch and a bit idealistic, even arrogant? Am I stuck in the past? After all, the professor, surrounded by his faculty colleagues, did not appear at all embarrassed and did not beat around the bush; why should I?

The year that passed since last summer’s workshop brought with it lessons in humility for me and for many of my colleagues. Technological innovations were emerging at such speed that I eventually had to admit to myself that I was, indeed, stuck in the past. The first time that I sat for conversation with ChatGPT was earlier this year here at Iscte, during an informative four-session course entitled “Inteligência Artificial Generativa no Ensino e Investigação” and taught by António Lopes, which proved to be a helpful point of entry. During the course’s first session, I recall testing the Large Language Model (LLM) by prompting an image of my home town in Israel under missile attack. My digital interlocutor refused, but could be coaxed into mocking up an image of the town under alien invasion. I was blown away by the technology, though less by its ethical reasoning in handling my prompts. Another recollection from that first encounter relates to my interlocutor’s tendency to confidently blend together factual and misleading information,

especially on esoteric topics, where knowledge gaps could quickly be filled with unaccounted-for hallucinations. As Lopes explained in that first session, LLMs are geared towards probability—frequency within training datasets—rather than factuality. I wondered, could such gravitation towards the median truly help to crack, say, Horizon Europe’s ERC requirements, that advertise for breakthrough, out-of-the-box, “high risk/high gain” project proposals? Well, maybe with the right prompt it could. According to my colleagues, AI is already a companion in writing highly competitive grants such as ERCs. While not yet replacing us, the final arbitrators, such developments raise questions about the relevance of our skillsets and role as professors and researchers. Weren’t we told that intellectual jobs will be the last ones to be automated, that academic positions are secure?

Stories from around the world show AI spreading quickly across academia, and it is not difficult to understand why. Optimising output and time use is not simply a question of indulgence but is often integral to the struggle for professional relevance and survival. When careers depend on satisfying university funding and publication quotas, in circumstances of fierce competition, professional overwork, and multitasking, the temptation to optimise—and at times, to cut corners—is undeniable. In my case, I am also expecting my first child in just a few months, at which point I am likely to turn even more optimisation-minded and more careful with time use. I recently learned that Google is working on a new generation of active voice assistance that you could send off on missions, for example, “please call three plumbers in Lisbon to check how much it would cost to fix the sink, and then coordinate with the cheapest among them to get to work next Tuesday”. Who wouldn’t want that while taking care of a baby next to a full-time job? Furthermore, even if I was to resist incorporating AI into my life-cum-work, the competitive nature of academic submissions is such that I fear being left behind in the digital-assistants arms race. I already brace myself that my next big project submission will take place in an altogether different environment.

What’s more, all of this is happening within an academic landscape that is not short of ambiguity, and the neck-breaking speed of transformation plays on preexisting grey zones. While plagiarism has long been a terrible no-no and while we fall for the allure of personal academic brilliance, we also internalized that academia is about “standing on the shoulders of giants” and that we should always chart the genealogies that led to our magnificent new discoveries. At the same time, the lines between outside inspiration and appropriation of someone else’s idea—their intellectual property—are not always clear-cut. Our learning grows in relations to others, whether through reading or through dialogue. In research teams, continuous exchange brings about intellectual entanglements that make it difficult to trace who first came up with which idea. Furthermore, the argument goes, if it is legitimate to rely on input from a research assistant, a grad student, or a professional academic editor or consultant—as many academics do—then how would that be different to using AI tools, which, if anything, level the playing field for those with inferior

academic infrastructure and less resources? For my colleagues in western Kenya, excitement about AI seems to be linked, among other things, to an understandable desire to offset some of the structural inequalities that keep them and their department less internationally competitive.

By and by, AI seems to be popping everywhere around us, from healthcare diagnosis tools to digital call centers. Magical AI buttons has been appearing in key software in areas as dissimilar as video communication and qualitative data analysis, and when I type a question into my Chrome browser, the top of the page now shows a tailored answer courtesy of Google's Gemini. I recently dipped my toes in the world of educational AI chatbots by starting to learn Finnish from a bot called Emma, who sends me flirtatious daily requests to tell her—in Finnish, of course—all about my favourite movies. But what about the limits of AI's incursion into the world of research? I had thought about AI as akin to imagination, lucid dreaming, or at most a hologram, with boundless ability to tell stories but with tenuous grasp over the concrete physical world. As an anthropologist researching international development, I rest assured that at least two aspects of my work are irreplaceable, for now: first, data collection—which for me requires in-situ fieldwork built around human interaction—and second, translation of findings into action, for example through stakeholder consultations, live lectures, and position papers. However, the line between the real and the virtual seems fuzzier and fuzzier. Similarly to Michael Ende's *Neverending Story*, where possessing the powerful Ayrin amulet grants boundless power of manipulation that blurs the line between imagination and reality, so does AI increasingly jump out from the screen to manipulate the physical world. Just the other day, a colleague sent me an AI-generated final report for an upcoming workshop that we are organizing in Tanzania. Before I had the time to read the mock-up, the colleague already complemented it with a convincing-looking article that will supposedly appear in next year's edition of a Q1 Africanist journal. What I found especially disconcerting was that that mock-up—a fabricated narrative from beginning to end, full of invented names of participants and interlocutors, and whose very author does not exist—was actually not a bad read. While schematic and dull at times, it did contain a couple of nifty ideas that I can imagine putting into use at the workshop itself. Ethnographers are often advised to set aside their preconceptions and expectations before going to the field, but how would it be to go to the field after reading the detailed, alleged conclusions of your own study-to-be? We are currently contemplating the integration of the pretend publication within the workshop's preparatory reading. What would be the impact of such a strange feedback loop between machine imagination and reality, between hypothetical and actual futures? How would our projects—nay, our very lives!—change if we caught an early glimpse of its retrospective retelling?

There is an element of mockery to all of this, which might explain many people's resistance, including my own. When I sent the mock-up article to my Tanzania workshop co-organizer, she simply replied, sneering "... An AI generated fake article?" I get it. It feels sometimes like we are looked down at by a machine that, while perhaps not in possession of a crystal ball, has more,

faster, and better-connected synapses, and is actually quite smug about it too. It makes me think of the famous Jewish verse, from the second-century text *Chapters of the Forefathers*: “everything is written in advance, and freedom of choice is granted”. But how could both things be true: divine determinism alongside complete human agency? The rabbis explain that this apparent paradox is due to competing qualities of the divine: God is omniscient, yes, but he is just as omnibenevolent, and as such, he graciously lets us make our own mistakes, rooting for us and shedding a tear as we inevitably stumble. That the results of the Tanzania workshop were “published” before the actual event even took place, with such brazen—seamless and shameless—mixture of the imagined and the real, conjures such a temporal and ontological muddle that make me resort to theology, you see. Against AI’s striving for omniscience, I see my colleagues honing in on human flaws as a welcome point of orientation: in this new era, a student submission that looks too well-written, too crisp in its articulation, is bound to raise suspicion. Many students, aware of that, intentionally undo some of the neatly laid sentences; like among rug weavers in some Islamic traditions, perfection is the prerogative of AI and Allah.

How, then, should I approach the question next time, should I again be invited to give that grant-writing workshop in Kenya? Well, I hope they do invite, as that would be a recognition that we haven’t done away with human academic expertise quite yet. And hopefully by then, I will be more prepared and won’t be taken aback by the AI question or see it as an affront. Even with AI breaking through the campus gates, there is plenty of work for us humans—to envision and to arbitrate, to collect and to manage. Who knows, maybe it is an opportunity to push ourselves all one notch higher, to revisit and even update Academia’s core mission. AI is here to stay, it seems, and time will tell if it is a boon to science or not. However, if we come to see academia exclusively in terms of box-ticking for degree or promotion, if we put unrealistic pressures on both students and staff, or otherwise force ourselves into neoliberal Darwinism of “survival of the optimised”, then desperation will surely feed temptations for AI to be promoted from a supportive role to a full-blown ghost writer.

And then, there is also the mess that is the state of our world in which this revolution is unfolding. If academia is indeed committed to the idea that knowledge is power, and transformative power at that, then it should be at the forefront of harnessing the incredible new technology to advance solutions to the uncertain state of our planet and societies. If AI outcompetes us in data retrieval and in the language model game, then perhaps academics should take the hint and move more decisively into the realm of human action, owning those real-world spaces where we still have an advantage: engaging in public outreach, communicating recommendations to political stakeholders, investing in extended in-person fieldwork, and building bridges of understanding between distant communities. There is so much more at stake than generating shortcuts for student papers and for bolstering academic CVs, and perhaps therein lies a partial answer. How will academics mobilize the revolution to reassess what matters most and to tackle concrete

global problems? AI may give the allure of omniscience, but for now, at least, it still awaits our prompt.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Funding

Funded by the European Union (ERC, AfDevLives, Project n° 101041788). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.